

SHERLOC: INNOVATIVE MANUFACTURING AND STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF THERMOPLASTIC STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

SHERLOC project is a European project framed within CleanSky research programme funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme. SHERLOC tries to respond the industrial needs regarding the structural health monitoring of real new generation aerospace structures.

The project looks for the manufacturing of innovative aerostructures and structural health monitoring techniques which allow the detection of possible issues on the structures during in-service, such as impacts or strikes. A Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic (CFRTP) window frame demonstrator was manufactured using woven CF/PEEK material supplied by Toho-Tenax. The selected manufacturing process was press-forming in a hot-press. Thermoplastic composites have been under the spotlight of the aerospace industry for decades due to the many advantages that may offer, such as recyclability, good mechanical performance and the opportunity of new out-of-autoclave manufacturing processes. To evaluate the quality of the thermoplastic window frame, some physical-chemical and mechanical testing were performed, including void content analysis, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and plain-compression testing. In addition to that, ultrasonic non-destructive inspection (NDI) was performed to evaluate the quality of the manufacturing process.

In addition of innovative thermoplastic structures, aerospace industry has been investing in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) technologies for many years to come to an industrial solution. Thus, a strategy was defined to monitor damages on thermoplastic structures, by combining elastic waves propagated through the structure, using piezoelectric (PZT) sensors. SHERLOC project will assess piezoelectric (PZT), fiber optic (FO) and hybrid (PZT-FO) based techniques to perform the SHM of aeronautical structures. The scope of this paper is the evaluation of the piezoelectric based techniques when applied to the monitoring of the thermoplastic window frame.

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Union (EU) has been developing technological aerospace projects via different programmes framed in Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, such as CleanSky2. SHERLOC project [1] (Structural Health Monitoring, Manufacturing and Repair Technologies for Life Management Of Composite Fuselage) is framed inside Green Regional Aircraft of CleanSky2, with the main goal of improving the readiness level of structural health monitoring (SHM) methods of aircraft real structures.

With an initial duration of 7 years (2015-2022), SHERLOC project is mainly focused on the integration of several SHM technologies, including piezoelectric transducers (PZT) [2–4], Fiber Bragg Grating optical sensors (FBG) [5], hybrid methods and also magnetoresistive sensors [5,6]. This, combined with innovative wireless communication devices [8], may lead to SHM methods to higher TRLs (Technology Readiness Level).

For the testing and validation of the monitoring technologies, composite materials specimens have been manufactured at different levels of the testing pyramid including: coupons, elements and sub-components. At coupon level, the sensors are implemented for validation into the specimens and their response behavior under different events is studied, such as vibration, humidity, strain and impact. The strategies of bonding/embedding for some of the sensors are optimized, but also the number of sensors required and their location in a real structure for reliable SHM is also studied.

At element and sub-component level, more complex geometries are manufactured. Some of those structures are floor beams, flat stiffened panels, curved stiffened panels and window frame. Different composite materials and methods are used for the manufacturing of the parts, including typical thermoset autoclave curing, but also liquid resin infusion (LRI) and thermoplastic processing.

In this study, several results of the SHERLOC project are presented, mainly focused on the manufacturing process and quality control of a thermoplastic window frame and the incorporation of PZT sensors for SHM activities, such as the monitoring of impacts.

2 THERMOPLASTIC WINDOW FRAME

In this section, all the information regarding the manufacturing of a thermoplastic window frame is described, including the associated quality control.

The selected manufacturing process for the thermoplastic window frame was compression molding in a hot platen press. This manufacturing method was selected owing to the fact that thermoplastic prepreg-based composite laminates can be moulded and consolidated in a single step with no need of extra consolidation cycles in oven or autoclave. Once the window frame was manufactured, quality control is required, by means of ultrasonic NDT (C-scan), void content analysis and DSC. With this quality control, the authors were able to check the degree of consolidation of the manufactured part, the level of void content into the structure and also the degree of crystallization, which is related with the cooling rate and the final mechanical performance of the structure. In addition to that, the first manufactured window frame of a series was cut-off to obtain coupons mechanical analysis by means of plain-compression testing.

2.1 Materials and configuration

For the manufacturing of thermoplastic window frames, the material Tenax® TPCL PEEK-4-40-HTA40 3K supplied by Toho-Tenax was selected. The material consists of a CF/PEEK fabric 5HS (5 harness satin) with 0.31mm nominal thickness per ply, 40% of resin content in weight and a fiber areal weight (FAW) of 285 gsm.

The stacking sequence of the window frame was selected after performing finite elements analysis (FEA) taking into account the typical load scenario of an in-service fuselage. The final stacking sequence of the element is $[(+45/-45)_4,(0/90)_2]_s$, resulting in a 11 plies element with 3.43mm nominal thickness.

2.2 Manufacturing process

The main steps during the manufacturing of the thermoplastic window frames are shown in Fig. 1. The manufacturing starts from ply cutting and hand lay-up of the preform. Due to the lack of tackiness

in thermoplastic prepreg materials, a manual welder was required for the application of welding points to join the plies. The position of the welding points should be shifted between plies to avoid manufacturing induced defects. A two-modules tooling (male and female) were used during the process with four positioning pins to fix the laminate positioning. Polyimide (Kapton) release films were used to facilitate demoulding activities.

The consolidation cycle was performed with a heat ramp of 2-4°C/min up to 390±10°C followed by a consolidation dwell time of 20 min. Then, the set-up was cooled down to room temperature, with a cooling down of 1-2°C/min to ensure a proper degree of crystallinity which do not compromise the final mechanical performance of the part [9,10]. After the consolidation cycle, the element was trimmed to final dimensions, which is some shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 Manufacturing steps of the consolidation process of the window frame: (a) Prepreg thermoplastic material roll. (b) manual plies cutting. (c) Hand- lay-up, using a manual welder to fix plies. (c) Tooling with polyimide (kapton) plies used as release film. (d) Tooling inside the hot press during consolidation cycle.

Fig. 2 Thermoplastic window frame after trimming

2.3 Quality control

Once the thermoplastic window frames were manufactured, typical industrial quality control for aerospace thermoplastic composite parts was performed, including ultrasonic NDT and void content assessment, but also adding DSC and mechanical testing.

2.3.1 Ultrasonic NDT

For ultrasonic NDT, double-trough transmission technique was selected, locating the specimen inside a water tank between the probe and a reflector plate. Automated TRITON 8000 TT+ equipment supplied by Tecnitest was used, working at a frequency of 5MHz

During the ultrasonic inspection, c-scans were generated in amplitude and attenuation (in dB) modes which were analysed for reporting the quality of the manufactured part. Amplitude and attenuation c-scans of a manufactured window frame are shown in Fig. 3

Fig. 3 Amplitude C-scan of the window frame (up) and attenuation (in dB) c-scan of window frame (bottom).

2.3.2 Void content assessment

Void content is a key parameter to be assessed when CFRP consolidation quality is evaluated. Void (or pores) content of the window frame laminate was assessed following the method B of the standard UNE-EN 2564 [11]. The principle of this test method is the determination of the difference in mass of specimens before and after extraction of the resin by sulphuric acid. In addition to void content, fibre and resin volume fractions are obtained applying this test method.

Four 20 x 10 x 3.2 mm coupons were extracted from window frame for this analysis. First, the density of each coupon was determined following the test method A of UNE-EN ISO 1183-1 [12]. Then, the resin was removed by means of acid digestion with sulphuric acid in a sand bath at 260 °C (thermoplastics with melting temperature ≥ 250 °C). Considering the values for resin density (D_r) and fibre density (D_f) provided by the material supplier (D_r : 1.30 g/cm³, D_f : 1.76 g/cm³), the results shown in the Table 1 have been obtained.

Table 1 Results of void content assessment (CV: Coefficient of Variation).

	Average result	Standard Deviation	CV (%)
<i>Void Volume, V_h (%)</i>	0.5	0.1	21
<i>Fibre Volume, V_f (%)</i>	56.0	0.5	0.9
<i>Resin Volume, V_r (%)</i>	43.5	0.5	1.0
<i>Fibre mass, W_f (%)</i>	63.6	0.5	0.7
<i>Resin mass, W_r (%)</i>	36.4	0.5	1.3

2.3.3 DSC

The temperatures and heat flows associated to the thermal transitions of the thermoplastic laminate were measured through Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) technique according to UNE-EN ISO 11357-3 [13]. Thus, temperatures and enthalpies of melting and crystallization were determined.

Two composite samples were extracted from the window frame. The weights of these samples were in the range of 20.5±0.5 mg. DSC analysis were performed by means of calibrated Q200 equipment from TA Instruments. Dynamic tests were performed with a heating rate of 20 °C/min from room temperature up to 400 °C followed by a 5-min isotherm. A cooling rate of 10 °C/min was then performed.

Considering the experimental fibre content, 63.6% (w/w), the results of these tests are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Results of Differential Scanning Calorimetry.

	Average result	Deviation	CV(%)
<i>Melting enthalpy, ΔH_m (J/g)</i>	17.5	0.51	3.1
<i>Initial temperature of melting point, T_{ELM} (°C)</i>	329	0.22	0.1
<i>Melting point, $T_{P,M}$ (°C)</i>	342	0.01	0.0
<i>Crystallization enthalpy, ΔH_c (J/g)</i>	16.1	0.42	2.6
<i>Initial temperature of crystallization point, T_{ELC} (°C)</i>	301.5	0.31	0.1
<i>Crystallization point, $T_{P,C}$ (°C)</i>	297.5	0.33	0.1
<i>Degree of crystallinity, χ (%)</i>	36.9	0.01	2.8

Where degree of crystallinity, χ , has been evaluated as follows:

$$X = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_f(1-\alpha)}$$

Where ΔH_m is the enthalpy of fusion at melting point, ΔH_c is the enthalpy of cold crystallization (it is not observed in our case), ΔH_f is the enthalpy of the completely crystalline polymer (130 J/g) and α refers to the weight fraction of carbon fibre within the laminate.

As seen in **Table 2**, the average value of the degree of crystallinity of the window frame determined during DSC testing is 36.9%. This value should not interfere with the mechanical performance of the structure, due to the fact that it is above 35%, which is reported in the literature as the optimal value for mechanical performance [14]

2.3.4 Mechanical testing

Compression tests were conducted according to the standard ASTM D6641/D6641M [15] in order to check the reproducibility of the mechanical test results. Five specimens were extracted from the window frame for compressive properties assessment. The tests were performed by means of a Universal Testing Machine Zwick Z250, equipped with a load cell up to 250 kN. Back-to-back strain gages 1-LY71-3 with a gage resistance of 350 Ω mounted on the centre of specimen faces were used to measure specimen strain. This type of strain gages allows to monitor bending or buckling along test execution, which is evaluated through percent bending. Maximum percent bending measured in these tests was 6%, thus test results can be considered as valid. The tests were conducted under Room Temperature conditions at a displacement rate of 1.3 mm/min. The results of these tests are shown in Table 3. Compressive strength and modulus are referred to nominal thickness.

Table 3 Results of compression tests.

	Average	Standard Deviation	CV (%)
Compressive strength (MPa)	363	4.14	1
Compressive modulus (GPa)	30.3	0.54	2

The failure mode for all of the coupons was brooming in the gage at the middle of the specimen. An example of this failure mode is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Example of failure mode of thermoplastic composite under compression loads.

2.3.5 Micrographic analysis

Optical micrographs and microstructural analysis were carried out to check lack of manufacturing defects in window frame laminate. Three samples were extracted from the window frame for microstructural analysis. A direct binocular microscope (Olympus BX61TRF) equipped with a camera of 5 megapixels was used for micrographic analysis. All samples required polished surface preparation and were analysed at different magnifications from 25x to 50x.

Fig. 5 Micrographs from sample 3 at (a) 25x and (b) 50x.

3 SHM OF THERMOPLASTIC MATERIALS BASED ON PZTS

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) aims to increase reliability and reduce maintenance costs in aeronautical structures. Reinforced matrix composites present some difficulties on the detection of structural damages (anisotropy, wave propagation, stiffness, etc.).

One of the most influential parameters for damage detection and characterization is the propagation velocity and, consequently, the Time of Flight (ToF). To determine this parameter in several directions, a PZT distribution has been performed as seen in the Fig. 6. In addition, a pitch-catch configuration was carried out (emission by one channel and acquisition by the rest), being able to determine the parameters measuring the time between the emission of the pulse signal in the actuator and the arrival of the propagated signal in the sensor, as well as the distance between both transducers. As seen in Fig. 6, the material is quasi-isotropic.

Fig. 6 Velocity chart on each direction (left). Time of Flight graph (right)

In order to characterize the material for damage detection based on PZTs [1], and thus determine the best way to detect damages, small dimensions (240 mm x 240 mm x 2.79 mm) coupons (Fig. 7)

were analyzed, using PZTs (DuraAct Patch Transducers, 17x13/D10x0,2 from PiCeramic) bonded to their surface. The excitation of these transducers with electrical signals produces elastic waves (Lamb waves), which propagate over the surface. The comparison between signals of a pristine state and a damaged state (in this case, a simulated damage using a piece of blu-tack), allow to detect and localize the damage using a probabilistic detection algorithm [16].

Fig. 7 Analyzed coupon from thermoplastic matrix composite with 12 PZT transducers. (a) Pristine state. (b) Simulated damaged location ($x=75$ mm, $y=165$ mm). (c) Prediction of the damage location.

In order to test the effectiveness of Lamb wave propagation for the developing of SHM systems in a piece of complex geometry, such as the window frame depicted in Fig. 8 (left), several PZTs were bonded to the outer surface of this piece, 4 of them in the inner ring and one of them in the outer ring. This last one allows to assess the wave propagation in the curved profile.

Fig. 8 Window frame with bonded transducers (left). Lamb waves signals obtained from the window frame PZTs, using a tone burst of 5 cycles, hamming windowing, 300 kHz, 20 Vpp (right)

The propagation of the waves over the coupon is complex due to its geometry and the proximity of the sensors to the edges, which causes multiple rebounds which are difficult to assess. However, in the first pulses after the arrival of the wave to the receiver transducer through the direct path (when rebounds are not present yet), it is possible to analyze the signals propagated from the transmitter transducer, obtaining signals similar to the depicted in Fig. 8 (right).

Finally, a damage was simulated (blu-tack) in a direct path between transducers, in this case in the path 2-3, as depicted in Fig. 9. The attenuation in that path is noticeable (the correlation coefficient decreases from $\rho=0.9999$ to $\rho=0.9407$, using the same parameters of excitation), which means a damage is present in that path and it is possible to detect its presence.

Fig. 9 (a) Location of the simulated damage. (b) Comparison between signals of path 2-1 before and after damage. (c) Difference between signals of path 2-3 before and after damage (350 kHz, 20 Vpp, 5 cycles hamming windowing).

Fig. 10 summarizes the correlation coefficient between signals in both states, in all the direct paths between transducers. It is remarkable that the coefficient decreases in all transducer pairs in which the simulated damage is present in the direct path, while the coefficient's value is close to one in the other ones.

Fig. 10 Correlation coefficient values for every paths.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, some of the results of SHERLOC project have been presented. A thermoplastic (CF/PEEK fabric) was successfully manufactured using out-of-autoclave methods. Compression molding technology was selected for the manufacturing of the window frame. Typical aerospace quality control methods were carried out in order to check the manufacturing quality of the element, including ultrasonic C-scan, void content and DSC analysis.

Void content of the window frame laminate is low and it accomplishes the requirements for advanced composite aerospace structures, for which void levels are acceptable up to 1% [17] Likewise, temperatures associated to the thermal transitions are in good agreement with those reported by the material manufacturer. Compression properties show low level of dispersion, which is a

positive evidence of the laminate homogeneity. Micrographic analysis is consistent with the ultrasonic and mechanical results of this study and does not reveal any major defect.

The validation of PZT based systems for the development of SHM strategies for monitoring thermoplastic structures has been assessed in this work. The propagation of Lamb waves generated by the excitation of PZT transducers can be used to detect damages or structural changes from the pristine state of the structure. In regular and simple thermoplastic coupons, these techniques allow to detect, locate and characterize the damage, while in more real and complex structures, such as the window frame used in the experiments, the detection of damages is still possible, but predicting their location and characterization is a more complex task, beyond the scope of this work.

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